

African Initiated Churches

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African Initiated Churches, otherwise also known as African Independent Churches and Pentecostal-Charismatic Churches (see Birgit Meyer) denotes a group of religious individuals brought together by the need to appropriate Christianity with traditional African belief systems. The term 'African Initiated Churches' thus categorises clusters of religious groupings formally termed the Zionist, Ethiopian and Messianic Churches. Since Christianity is expanding rapidly in Africa, recent theorists suggest that the threefold categorisation fails to capture the complexity and vibrancy of said religious groups; distinguishing rather between followers of the 'Book' and the 'Word' (see M Nel). For this entry, we focus primarily on the Zion Christian Church (ZCC) in South Africa. The group derives its name and theological bent from a variety of sources. Historically, the Scottish-Australian minister John Alexander Dowie who went to America and started the city of Zion movement which emphasised healing had a great influence on the formation of the Zionist churches in Africa. For example, Dowie exerted significant influence over the local South African Dutch Reformed missionary, Pieter L Le Roux, who became increasingly interested in the matter of healing after reading Dowie's works and coming across localised testimonies of healing. After resigning from the Dutch Reformed Church (DRC), Le Roux started a church for all members in South Africa which included Zulu speaking individuals. As M Nel writes, 'Le Roux's Zionist group was characterised by their accommodation to indigenous habits and beliefs. The worship was lively and loud and the clothing colourful' (See Nel, p. 206). Le Roux is thus credited with starting the Zionist movement in South Africa. A Biblical thematic central to both Dowie and Le Roux was the concept of the cultic centre (see Kelebogile Resane). In Hebrew Scriptures the Mount of Zion represented a centralised place of congregation and worship of God. In many respects it also represented the promises of Yahweh to the Jewish nation. Since Mount Zion also served as a place of ritual and worship, life itself was centred around the holy place. Zion City in Moria, Limpopo, has come to denote a similarly theologically significant place for the believers within the ZCC. Twice yearly all members are encouraged to participate in worship during the Easter festival and in September. The ZCC and its African initiated affiliates were long overlooked in religious and theological inquiry because the emphasis on faith healing and the appreciation of African traditional practices was regarded as functioning outside of the theological. As a result religious phenomenon was relegated to the sociological and anthropological. Recent theological inquiry shows, however, a great wealth of knowledge that is just beginning to be uncovered by modern day scholars. Due to the fact that the ZCC and its annual meetings, in particular, are kept private and rarely opened to media, the information at researchers' disposal is scant.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Moria, Limpopo, South Africa

Region tags: Africa, South Africa

This map represents the country of South Africa in the larger polygon, to demonstrate reach of the popularity of the church throughout South Africa. A smaller polygon, which will appear as a dot when zoomed out, represents the approximate location of Moria, Limpopo province, which is the church's headquarters.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: PL Le Roux, Dutch Reformed Missionary, Zionist Preacher and Leader of the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa, and the Origin of some of the African Independent Churches in Southern Africa. By M Nel., Ned. geref. theologiese tydskrif, 2005-03-01, Vol.46 (1_2), p.200-208
- Source 2: African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in South Africa. By K T Resane., Scriptura 119 (2020:1), pp. 1-16.
- Source 3: Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. By C H Grundmann., International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church Vol. 6, No. 3, October 2006, pp. 256 - 269.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.dailymaverick.co.za/article/2012-04-10-moria-the-road-to-zion/>
- Source 1 Description: Easter Pilgrimage Description
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.sahistory.org.za/article/zion-christian-church-zcc>
- Source 2 Description: Informal study of the history of the ZCC's development.
- Source 3 URL: https://www.huffingtonpost.co.uk/2017/04/07/identity-and-faith-church-uniforms-in-south-africa_a_22030625/
- Source 3 Description: On uniforms, songs and expectations.

Notes: There is a plethora of information available - especially media on the ZCC's annual Easter Pilgrimage - as well as how it funds itself at the following YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lcuh4rE1XIA> Please note that the video is very old and should serve as reference point only.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/c/ZCCMbungo>
- Source 1 Description: The ZCC's official YouTube channel

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

- No

Notes: A primary feature of the Zion Christian Church, and so also the African Initiated Churches, is its focus on unity, collaboration and cooperation.

Reference: Kelebogile Resane Thomas. African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in South Africa. *Scriptura*, 119(1)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The ZCC recognises that every person lives in the surroundings governed by the activity of spirits. Such spirits can, sometimes, be harnessed by others to affect a person's life in a positive or negative way. These spirits are called 'umoya'. The transformative message of the ZCC lies in the power of the Holy Spirit, the uMoya, who has final authority over all other spirits. Said conception of the Third Person of the Trinity 'appeals to people longing for enhancement and preservation of life's power, but especially to those who are socially and economically marginalised...' (see Grundmann, pp. 264 - 265)

Reference: Christoff Grundmann H. Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. *International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church*, 6(3) issn: 1747-0324. doi: 10.1080/14742250600877125.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There have been instances of conflict between ZCC members and the general public. Most occurrences took place during the periods of segregation in South Africa. The ZCC leadership invited controversial white political figures in South Africa to two of their annual meetings (1980 and 1985). Individuals in Johannesburg came to hear of this and were outraged by it. As a result, ZCC members were targeted and sometimes attacked. In 1992 three political leaders were invited. This time, however, all members represented were associated with a changing (more peaceful) political landscape in South Africa. (See Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps)

Reference: Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps Zion Christian Church

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents generally gain salvation through baptism - threefold immersion - alongside the confession of belief in the Father, Son and Holy Spirit.

Reference: Zion Christian Church

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Men and women have different roles within the Zionist churches. Although they are deemed equal, women and men participate in different worship ceremonies at times. Women also fulfil leadership roles in the church.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Persons become part of the ZCC through threefold immersion understood as baptism.

Reference: Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps Zion Christian Church

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Members are encouraged to go to the annual gathering at Zion City, Moria, Limpopo.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the ZCC wear a medal/badge every day of their life as a symbol of their association with the ZCC, their participation in Christianity and their commitment to the lifestyle prescribed by the ZCC.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Even though the ZCC does not elicit political support, because its membership is so vast (an estimated 2 - 6 million in South Africa) political leaders find it advantageous to attend the annual Easter summit. A further contributing factor is that the bishop of the ZCC exerts tremendous influence and so ensuring that there exists a good understanding between an individual with a vested interest and the bishop is paramount. A final consideration in view of the recent Covid pandemic is that since millions of believers attend the annual Easter celebration, the South African government has engaged in discussion surrounding advisable and non-advisable practices.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: There is a great deal of information on the rituals, beliefs and practices of the ZCC but little about the event where an individual no longer wishes to be part of the ZCC. Further research needs to be done on this.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 5000000

Notes: The estimated population is based on the 2001 South African census. Numbers are likely to have grown significantly. Approximately 1,300,000 individuals attend the annual Easter celebration and September celebrations. (See Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps)

Reference: Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps Zion Christian Church

Reference: Zion Christian Church (ZCC)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 35

Notes: An estimated 35% of the black population in South Africa (at 2000) were members of the African Independent Churches in South Africa. The particular % figure for ZCC adherents within the African Initiated Churches cannot be measured.

Reference: M Nel. PL Le Roux, Dutch Reformed Missionary, Zionist Preacher and Leader of the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa, and the Origin of some of the African Independent Churches in Southern Africa. *Ned. geref. teologiese tydskrif*, 46(1)

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The ZCC has a high regard for the 'Book' of the Christian faith, the Bible. It plays a central role in that there are core themes in both the New Testament and the Old Testament which are reappropriated to the particular cultural experiences and needs of adherents.

Reference: Kelebogile Resane Thomas. African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in South Africa. *Scriptura*, 119(1) doi: 10.7833/119-1-1768.

Reference: Christoff Grundmann H. Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. *International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church*, 6(3)

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: Although there is not a formal oral scripture there is a formal oral tradition where song and story telling plays a central role in maintaining the religious narrative of the ZCC.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: As part of the Christian tradition, the ZCC follow the same beliefs as Christians universally over the origins of the Bible.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Notes: Of interest is that the very first bishop of the ZCC, Joseph Engenas Matlhakanye Lekganyane, who established the church in 1924 and was trained by Scottish Presbyterian Missionaries, influenced by the American Zion movement and shaped by the socio-economic changes underwent in South Africa during the 1920s, was seen to be an African Messiah. Joseph's son and later grandson, however, moved away from this notion with a focus falling more on the 'Book'.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The Bible is highly regarded and seen to be the singular text from which preaching, praying and living is derived.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: None other than preachers expounding on Scriptures in their sermons.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Whether these individuals are formally trained is not clear.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious

monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: The ZCC do not have a monument as such rather than a cultic centre to which millions of believers flock each year. Zion City located in Moria, Limpopo, South Africa. It is not possible, therefore, to estimate what percentage of area the city takes up in relation to the rest of the believing community.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 5.06

Notes: See note above

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Followers trek to Moria, Limpopo, as and when is possible.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The ZCC is well known for its emphasis on corporeality. Here, the body is the mechanism through which the Holy Spirit and other spirits - such as ancestors - have a role to play. The distinction which thus exists between the human spirit and body is one of purpose and function. The spirit (as in a person's spirit) can respond to any other spirit (ancestral or divine) through the body. Likewise, when the body is affected (positively or negatively) the spirit can respond to that by invoking the supreme God.

Reference: Thabang Mofokeng Richard. Zionist 'syncretism' in the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa before the 1970s - A Comparative Analysis. *Missionalia*, 49(1) issn: 2312-878X.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

Notes: There is no distinction between mind and matter, so to speak. What happens in the realm of the corporeal is what happens in the realm of the human spirit. There is a direct correlation and relationship between the two.

Reference: Christoffer Grundmann H. Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. *International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church*, 6(3) issn: 1747-0324. doi: 10.1080/14742250600877125.

Reference: Thabang Mofokeng Richard. Zionist 'syncretism' in the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa before the 1970s.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The ZCC has a very rich understanding of the spirit world. Spirits can influence a person's being - the whole being - including the mind and the thoughts that it cultivates. One must realise, however, that the distinction made here is not akin to the Western Cartesian distinction of body and mind. One can only thus approach the question by addressing the mind first and the spirit second. The mind is entirely connected to and integrated with the body and its functioning - whatever presents itself within this realm, is as much a manifestation of the corporeal as the spiritual. The spirit, or spiritual, falls within the realm of the hereafter - that of those who have gone before, and as such, the ancestral. Ancestors have the power to exert influence on an individual. The influence which ancestors exert is very much dependent on whether their deeds were good or evil. As a result, they can be invoked to either positively or negatively influence a person's life, decisions or circumstances. When thus speaking of the spirit, one is alluding to the realm of the here and now as well as the hereafter.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The spirit world is one in which other spirits can affect an individual positively or negatively. In this sense, spirits sent by others can influence a person's spirit and their body. There are thus external spirits that can play a part in a person's corporeal existence.

Notes: Of interest is the African spirituality here which is by no means in conflict with the Judeo-Christian tradition that the ZCC upholds. To ask whether these are Christian or non-Christian spirits is to misunderstand an African Spirituality of those who have passed away. Other than the power of influence, ancestors have no divine status and as such, will be brought under the authority of the Holy Spirit if their intentions are not aligned with the good that is understood to come forth from God.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The prominence of a cultic centre lends itself in different ways to the eschatology of the ZCC. For believers, salvation is something situated in a mystical belief in the workings of the Trinity. The Holy Spirit then makes known to believers on a daily basis the peace which they can expect after death. While mention is made of a 'heaven', it is doubtful whether this is given a concrete/spatial location.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

Notes: As with the Christian tradition, the afterlife is understood to be a place of salvation, wholeness and healing. It is not understood to be a physical place.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: This is a metaphorical reference though and should not be taken to be literal.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Other than elaborate grieving ceremonies, the dead are buried and entrusted to God. There may be purification rituals also. More research is required on this matter though.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: The specificity of grave goods cannot be legitimately affirmed or negated here.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: It is crucial to realise that the ZCC follows a twofold trajectory - that which is inherited through the Christian tradition and that which is inherited by way of traditional spiritualities. The word 'syncretism' has been used to describe the relationship between the two but recent scholars are less enthusiastic about this designation, Mofokeng writes: 'The theological departures associated with Zionism, especially, attracted negative assessment from the missionary enterprise and the academy encapsulated in the term, "syncretism" (Shaw et al., 2016:102). However, the reappraisal by some in the academy shifted the negative connotations attached to the concept of syncretism, and eventually led to its abandonment in favour of "contextualisation", which was understood as translation of the gospel into into the indigenous cultural milieu.'

Reference: Thabang Mofokeng Richard. Zionist 'syncretism' in the Apostolic Faith mission of South Africa before the 1970s - A Comparative Analysis.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: In line with the Christian conception of God. Jesus Christ is seen to be God incarnate in human form. The Holy Spirit perpetually communicates this reality to individuals on a daily basis. The imperative of the ZCC to proclaim the Gospel includes the proclamation of a God who was both human and divine.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: The ZCC do not have deities attributed to different elements of the created order.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Certain religious leaders have received a vision or word from God.

Notes: A recurring theme within the pentecostal-charismatic movements in Africa, and also South Africa, is that of some form of divine revelation - i.e. where an individual understands him or herself to receive a unique message from God. The same is the case for the leadership of the ZCC.

Reference: Kelebogile Resane Thomas. African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in South Africa. Scriptura, 119(1)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: To question this would be to question the whole premise of having a divine and benevolent supreme being.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme God is transcendental, immanent and omnipresent.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The God of ZCC believers is all knowing.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Song, dance, prayer and narratives are used to contextualise positive emotions through the interpretation of Scripture.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as God may display displeasure with behaviour that is not congruent with what is laid out in the Christian Scriptures. Once more, song, dance and narrational exposition is used to draw implications to today's world.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through any other individual who is considered a 'brother' or

'sister' within the ZCC and broader Christian community.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: As a combination of what is conceived as traditional Christian beliefs and the marriage thereof with more indigenous beliefs, some may believe in human spirits whether it is actively preached by the presiding ministers or not. One thing that is clear is that traditional African beliefs, in South Africa, are very much focused on ancestors. Ancestors manifest themselves in the here and now although they are unseen. As a result, ancestors can be invoked and asked to bring prosperity and health to a particular person, family or circumstance.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Notes: The intricate cosmology of the ancestral world is something not often spoken of or elaborated. Finding credible information on this matter is rare.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: Possibly, the remit of what ancestors can know and the knowledge which they have of the future is very much based on the personalised narrative surrounding a particular individual. It is likely that the extent to which ancestors are believed to have knowledge of the past, present and future is based on an individual family, narrative or tradition.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Too little information is publicly known about the ways in which the ancestors engage with persons and how such persons either affirm or negate ancestral intentions.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Because the corporeal is so central in African traditional cultures, having an illness or some unfortunate event happen to you can be seen as a form of communication. Say, that something is not right or that a spirit is unhappy. Likewise, success and happiness can be seen as the positive reinforcement of a life approved of.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: There is a twofold distinction between the Holy Spirit that is the third person of the Trinity and 'manmade' spirits that come to affect an individual adversely. The Holy Spirit acts as safeguard against evil or demonic spirits.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: The spirit world of Sub-Saharan African traditions are very complex and can't be expounded without a depth of attention.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They can be harnessed by evil to affect a believer negatively. Such evil spirits should be resisted through prayer.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Only insofar as different spirits can cause different adverse things to happen in an individual's life. Due to the complex conception of the spirit world, further investigation is required before providing superficial responses.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: It is generally accepted that Zion, 'king Jesus', will come again but a time/date is not part of the eschatological orientation. (Grundmann)

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The Messiah will come to, once and for all, incorporate all those who have believed into the mystical body of Christ.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Believers are encouraged to abstain from pork, alcohol, tobacco and any other kind of pastime like gambling. Dancing is permitted only at celebratory occasions.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Strict adherence to the ZCC way of life is ensured. There is no mainline or conventional rendition of the ZCC.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The virtues pursued by the ZCC are very much aligned with the virtues advocated by the Christian Scriptures.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Pork, tobacco and alcohol is not permitted.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Members are encouraged to give a portion of their monthly income to the

churches for the purposes of advancing its message and members who may need it.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members very often go to church services, work in the community and take part in an annual journey to Moria for Easter.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: For the most part, the ZCC follows the Christian tradition. Of prominence within the ZCC are precepts that are practical and easily to apply in daily life.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: The ZCC is known for its ecumenism - it, accordingly, welcomes other African Initiated Churches and Mainline Churches' participation at certain shared religious events.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 1300000

Notes: As has been highlighted in previous sections, the number of attendants at the yearly Easter celebration can vary greatly but is estimated to start at 1,300,000.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 4320

Notes: Roughly two times a year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: Information on circumcision is not given as a prerequisite to belonging to the ZCC. Since African Initiated Churches mix traditional beliefs with Christianity, it may be that some believers may be circumcised as part of their culture or traditional beliefs.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Pork and alcohol is not permitted.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Women may cover their hair at moments of worship.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: All believers wear a ZCC medal which is fastened to clothing. Within Southern Africa the medal has become widely understood as the ZCC's. For some of the general public the medal gives assurance of an individuals' conduct and suitability to a given function within society. At the Easter celebration men have been seen to wear kaki suits with white leather shoes while women wear skirts and dresses. When attending a church service on a regular day, all members wear white clothing and gather in the open instead of buildings.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The ZCC is an African Initiated Church - as such the religious group belongs to the ecclesial family of churches in Southern Africa. While they have, for a long time, not been recognised for their religious contribution more globally, within Southern Africa the ZCC has functioned as a church since the 1920s.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: The ZCC has an extensive localised support basis where members are helped based on their needs. The help offered is not, however, institutionalised.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: While financial relief may be offered by fellow believers, there is no institutionalised service.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: On governmental level. There is no coordination between the government and the ZCC though.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government, charities and not for profits would provide this service.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: A major question hangs over the education of ZCC members as well as its leadership. This is due, in part, to the fact that members were formerly (especially prior to post-Apartheid South Africa) restricted from gaining education. In the same way, there is no formal/institutionalised ZCC training centre. Bishops are elected based on their direct affiliation to the first bishop - i.e., sons and grandsons.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: While the education may be open to males and females, that is not to say that women may preach at a Sunday service.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The hierarchy, roughly speaking, falls within the category of bishop, local preacher/minister and prophet. Matters are often handled on a local basis with church leadership and members finding resolutions in situations of conflict. If there is a matter that proves impossible to resolve, the bishop is sought for further guidance.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Average adherents don't engage with institutionalised bureaucracies. Occasionally the leadership has invited politicians to mass gatherings - some instances without disagreement from the public, other instances with resultant conflict.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Municipalities are supposed to provide water infrastructure. Unfortunately, this duty is not always performed. In such cases the general public as well as church members try to establish alternative initiatives.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Transport infrastructure is provided, in particular, when mass gatherings such as the Easter and September gatherings are held. These take the shape of buses, mini-buses and taxis.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: In some instances, members have to arrange for their transport to major events privately.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Church members do tithe. The exact percentage and whether this is policed by the leadership is not known. What is known is that local members pay the stipend for their minister - more often than not, they cannot meet the suggested stipend due to the fact that members may live in impoverished areas.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: At the Easter gathering security is used as a way of enforcing order. This is not institutionalised, however, and serves a momentary function.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: That security is used during major events is known but whether this is a privatised or public service is unknown.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: While there aren't any institutionalised judges, there are members of authority who preside over matters of conflict. They would be responsible for ensuring resolution between parties. As to whether such individuals deal with matters outwith the church's bounds is not known.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As per normal societal law and order members of the ZCC may take up a legal matter through the juridical court. There is no formal agreement, however, between such juridical services and the ZCC.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In South Africa, all members of the ZCC are punishable by the South African justice system in the event of illegal activity.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Little is known of the codes that govern the ZCC including their legal and ethical codes.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The South African governments' legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Possibly, but this would only be as a means of earning an income. As far as the information goes that relate to rules governing members of the ZCC there is little restriction on the work that individuals can do.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This would be general education.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As would be prescribed for individuals working and living in a traditionally South African context or contexts.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Two periods are important - those where members gather in masses for celebration. These include the Easter and September pilgrimages to Moria, Limpopo. Other than that, weeks are ordered by the need to attend services on a Wednesday, Saturday and Sunday.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: C Wapener , M Barnard. Worship in the Zion Christian Church (ZCC): A descriptive exploration of a prophetic phenomenon.. (H Kroesbergen, Ed.), Prophecy today: Reflections from a Southern African context. Wellington: Christian Literature Fund Publishers.

Reference: D Koto-Abuti B. African Theology/ies: A Contemporary Mosaical Approach. Bloomington: Authorhouse.

Reference: I Dlamini. Zionist Churches from the Perspective of a Zionist Church Leader. (Dlamini, G Oosthuizen C, Ed.), Religion Alive - Studies in the New Movements and Indigenous Churches in South Africa. Johannesburg: Hodder & Stoughton.

Reference: Kelebogile Resane Thomas. African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in South Africa. Scriptura, 119(1)

Reference: Ulf Strohhahn. The Zionist Churches in Malawi: History - Theology - Anthropology. Mzuni Press.

Reference: Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps Zion Christian Church

Reference: Jose da Silva Antunes. African Independent Churches Origin and Development. Anthropos, 88(4)

Reference: Jesse Mugambi , J Mugambi N.K. African Churches in Social Transformation. Journal of International Affairs, 50(1)

Reference: H Turner W. Problems in the Study of African Independent Churches. Numen, 13(1)

Reference: Birgit Meyer. Christianity in Africa: From African Independent to Pentecostal-Charismatic Churches.

Reference: C Wepener , M Barnard. Entering the Field: Initiating Liturgical Research in an African Independent Church (AIC). Acta Theologica, 30(2) issn: 1015-8758.

Reference: M Nel. PL Le Roux, Dutch Reformed Missionary, Zionist Preacher and Leader of the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa, and the Origin of some of the African Independent Churches in Southern Africa. Ned. geref. teologiese tydskrif, 46(1)

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Christoff Grundmann H. Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church, 6(3)

Reference: Kelebogile Resane Thomas. African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in

South Africaa. Scriptura, 119(1) doi: 10.7833/119-1-1768.

Reference: Zion Christian Church (ZCC)

Reference: Zion Christian Church

Reference: M Nel. PL Le Roux, Dutch Reformed Missionary, Zionist Preacher and Leader of the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa, and the Origin of some of the African Independent Churches in Southern Africa. Ned. geref. teologiese tydskrif, 46(1)

Reference: Johanneke Kroesbergen-Kamps Zion Christian Church , ,

Reference: Kelebogile Resane Thomas. African Zionism and its Contribution to African Christianity in South Africa. Scriptura, 119(1) ,

Reference: Christoff Grundmann H. Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church, 6(3) issn: 1747-0324. doi: 10.1080/14742250600877125.

Reference: Thabang Mofokeng Richard. Zionist 'syncretism' in the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa before the 1970s.

Reference: Thabang Mofokeng Richard. Zionist 'syncretism' in the Apostolic Faith Mission of South Africa before the 1970s - A Comparative Analysis. Missionalia, 49(1) issn: 2312-878X.

Reference: Christoffer Grundmann H. Heaven Below Here and Now! The Zionist Churches in Southern Africa. International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church, 6(3) issn: 1747-0324. doi: 10.1080/14742250600877125.

Reference: Thabang Mofokeng Richard. Zionist 'syncretism' in the Apostolic Faith mission of South Africa before the 1970s - A Comparative Analysis.